

The Canterbury School of Theodore of Tarsus and Hadrian the North African

By John Gallagher, University of St Andrews

Entry tags: Christianity, Roman Catholic, Christian, Catholic, Religious Group, Abrahamic, Roman Religious Traditions, Christianity, Rome, Monasticism, Celtic Religions, Christian Traditions, Germanic Religions, Religious Practice, Medieval Christianity

The Canterbury School was, loosely, a group of students, monastics, and clerics who operated under the tutelage and guidance of Theodore of Tarsus, Archbishop of Canterbury (sed. CE 668–69) and Hadrian the North African, Abbot of the Monastery of SS Peter and Paul, Canterbury (sed. CE 670–709/760). The School was located at Canterbury, the Primatial See of England and the heart of Roman Christianity in Britain, and constituted the principal monastic educational institution in Anglo-Saxon England. The group was formed of members of different local religious communities, ordinands from throughout the province, and scholars and clerics from further afield, namely Ireland, all of whom flocked to the Canterbury School because of the high quality of education available there. A number of generations of scholars, clergy, and professional religious personnel were trained at this centre of learning. The Canterbury School under its two illustrious masters represented a 'golden age' and an early high point – in England and early medieval Europe more broadly – for the study of Greek and Latin Patristics, Biblical exegesis, comparative Biblical-textual criticism, and erudite Christian learning, as the extant writings from the School attest.

Date Range: 669 CE - 690 CE

Region: Anglo-Saxon England (Early Medieval England)

Region tags: Europe, England

Anglo-Saxon England and early medieval England refer to the area of Britain that was settled by Germanic settlers and immigrants (continental Angles, Saxons, and Jutes) from ca. CE 450 onwards, which is roughly equivalent to modern-day England. These groups displaced and intermingled with the Celtic (British) and Romano-British people who already occupied the area. The region extended from Northumbria in the north to Wessex in the south-west and Kent in the south-east; the central part of the country was known as Mercia or Anglia.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: *Biblical Commentaries from the Canterbury School of Theodore and Hadrian*, Cambridge Studies in Anglo-Saxon England 10, edited by Bernhard Bischoff and Michael Lapidge (Cambridge:

Cambridge University Press, 1994).

– Source 2: Archbishop Theodore: Commemorative Studies on his Life and Influence, Cambridge Studies in Anglo-Saxon England 11 (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1995).

– Source 3: Michael Lapidge, 'The School of Theodore and Hadrian', Anglo-Saxon England 15 (1986): 45-72.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/book/10.1002/9781118316061>

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: There was stringent competition and disagreement between those churches in Britain and Ireland that followed Roman practices and those which followed local ('Celtic' or Irish) practices.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– Yes

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by class:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by gender:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– Yes [specify]: Coming to study at the Canterbury School and to learn from its masters despite whether or not one personally went on to promote these views.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– No

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– No

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– No

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– Yes

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– Yes

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– Field doesn't know

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Heresy is a concern in some texts surviving from the School. These represent historical heresies and contemporary concerns, but there is no evidence whether the heresies criticised in the sources were ever present in England. There is also concern with divergent liturgical and ecclesiastical practices.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: The Latin and Greek Bibles.

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– No

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– No

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– I don't know

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

- Field doesn't know

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

- Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

- Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

- Field doesn't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

- Yes

Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

- No

Is the messiah's purpose known:

- I don't know

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

- Field doesn't know

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

- I don't know

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Monogamy (males):

– Yes

Notes: Members of the group are clerics and, therefore, celibate.

Monogamy (females):

– Yes

Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:
i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– I don't know

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– I don't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– No

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– I don't know

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: The Canterbury School was an educational group and institution in early medieval England.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Field doesn't know

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Field doesn't know

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– Yes

Is such education open to both males and females:

– No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– I don't know

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– I don't know

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: Greek was studied and learned at the Canterbury School, which is unique for this period in the early medieval Latin West.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– I don't know

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know